

Logistics

All the documents that will be necessary for the workshop can be found in our [Gfolder](#).

- [Workshop agenda](#) for day 1 and day 2
- **Zoom** details:
 - [Zoom day 1](#), Oct 8, 14:00-18:00 CEST
 - [Zoom day 2](#), Oct 9, 14:00-18:00 CEST
- We ask people to check that their zoom names are their full name and the institute they represent. We also ask that as you join, you write your name, institute, and type of stakeholder that you are, in the chat. This is for our records, so that we know which institutes and projects have been represented.
- We will unmute the mics during the Q&A sessions and during the breakouts of both days.
- The Zoom chat can be used for questions, which we will answer during the workshop and after; someone will keep an eye on it for comments specifically on meeting-technical issues.
- We will be recording the plenary session and this will be provided along with the public workshop report. The breakouts will only be recorded to help create the meeting minutes.
- The workshop report will be provided in this same [Gfolder](#) and you will all have a chance to comment on it before it is finalised. For those of you who could not attend the workshop, that is also a way you can provide your input.
- All presentations will be accessible from the [Gfolder](#) after the workshop.

Who are the stakeholder groups?

We have divided the stakeholders in this eDNA data ecosystem into three:

- **A: publishers of DNA and biodiversity data.**
 - This means data publishers, not journals
 - It includes those that also create biodiversity data, as well as publish that
 - This includes any type of:
 - DNA data (sequences, ASV/OTU; metabarcoding, metagenomics, etc). Examples: ENA, NCBI
 - biodiversity data: those that publish organism identifications/occurrences and associated information. Example: GBIF, OBIS, EurOBIS/EMODnet, OpenBiodiv, iBoI
- **B: Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data)**
 - Reference libraries: those that provide reference libraries to be used to make taxonomic identifications. Examples: BOLD, UNITE
 - Bioinformatics: those who create or provide tools to run bioinformatics analysis
 - Taxonomies (data): those that provide authoritative taxonomic information and curated IDs. Can be “traditional” taxonomic names, and also those providing omics-based IDs (that is identifiers rather than names). Example: WoRMS taxonomy (former), NCBI taxonomy (former), BOLD BIN (latter). In this group, the discussion around taxonomy will focus on how taxonomic names and IDs are used in (meta)data
- **C: Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts)**
 - Biobanks and culture collections are those that store material/organisms and the information (metadata) relating to that material, in particular where this is related to material used for DNA analysis. Examples: CCAP, CEST.
 - Taxonomies (concepts): those that provide authoritative taxonomic information and curated IDs. Can be “traditional” taxonomic names, and also those providing omics-based PIDs (identifiers rather than names). Example: WoRMS (former), NCBI (former), BOLD (later). In this group the discussion around taxonomy will focus on the concepts of taxonomic classification of organisms, including issues of taxa that are difficult to classify, dealing with naming for (new, ongoing) scientific discoveries, etc.

General documents: eDNAqua-Plan and the Landscaping report

- [eDNAqua-Plan](#) is a Horizon Europe project that will develop a Roadmap towards a future eDNA digital ecosystem in Europe, within a *global* context.
 - eDNAqua-Plan project **Factsheet**:
<https://zenodo.org/records/15183570>
- Our mapping of the **current and proposed future landscape** can be found in <https://zenodo.org/records/16090825>.
 - **The full report** is provided as a PDF for download. It includes our analysis of the current landscape, from sample collection through to taxonomic identification, and all the (meta)data practices that are undertaken in the various stages. It lists “what works” and “what doesn’t work” for each stage. Recommendations for different practices are then made, to allow an evolution into a smoother future landscape. *These are the recommendations on which we will base this workshop.*
 - **Diagrams** of the current and future landscape are downloadable as JPG. *These are the diagrams on which we will base this workshop.* You will probably want to zoom in on the sections that are most relevant to you.

Day 1 discussion documents

Current landscape diagram

- [Current landscape diagram original](#): this has been copied from Zenodo
- [Current landscape diagram modified](#): the approximate areas of relevance for the different stakeholder groups (DNA data publishers, Biodiversity data publishers, Reference libraries, Taxonomic systems, Bioinformatics, Biobanks and Culture Collections) have been encircled.

Future landscape diagram

- [Future landscape diagram original](#): this has been copied from the Zenodo publication
- [Future landscape diagram modified](#): the approximate areas of relevance for the different stakeholder groups (DNA data publishers, Biodiversity data publishers, Reference libraries, Taxonomic systems, Bioinformatics, Biobanks and Culture Collections) have been encircled.

Day 1 breakouts

We have prepared a focussed [summary of the Landscaping report](#) which is the material to be discussed during the breakout sessions of Day 1. The questions that will be discussed during the breakouts are also given there.

The breakouts will use Miro boards. The Miro board link is:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVJNOsn4w=?share_link_id=602380831568, which takes you to the Workshop Landing Board. You will find instructions to use Miro, a copy of agenda, a copy of the Landscaping diagram, and links to the boards for the Day 1 Breakout session 1, 2 and 3, and Day 2 Breakouts A, B, and C. By clicking on the “Miro” name at the top left, you can get to the home page where you can also see a listing of all boards.

During day 1 you will be randomly assigned to one of the Breakouts 1,2 or 3, and based on where you find yourself, you will click on the link for the board for your session. We will keep using the Zoom call to be able to talk to each other during the session. At the end of the breakout, you will be automatically brought back to the plenary.

At the start of the breakout session you will be asked to start by adding your name and institute to the purple area. You should all now have editing access, which means we ask you please do not start doing anything on the board, other than looking at it, until the workshop. If you want to explore it beforehand, you can zoom in and out with your mouse, and centre- or right-mouse press-drag to move around (you may need to select the blue left-pointing “pan” arrow-head on the left-hand-side menu). Note: the board will not be completely ready until the workshop, i.e. we are still working on it.

Day 2 discussion documents

The same current and future landscape diagrams that you can find on [Day 1 discussion documents](#) will be useful on day 2 also.

In addition, the specific recommendations that will form the background to the discussion points for the three stakeholder group breakouts are summarised in these documents:

- [Stakeholder group A: DNA and biodiversity data publishers](#)
- [Stakeholder group B: Reference libraries, bioinformatics, taxonomic systems \(data\)](#)
- [Stakeholder group C: Biobanks, Culture Collections, taxonomies \(concepts\)](#)

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During day 2 you will be able to choose whether to join Breakouts A, B, or C. All breakouts A and B will be using a Miro board. Based on which breakout you have joined, you will click on the link for the board for your session. We will keep using the Zoom call to be able to talk to each other during the session. At the end of the breakout, you will be automatically brought back to the plenary.

You should all now have editing access to all boards, which means we ask you please do not start doing anything on the board, other than looking at it, until the workshop. If you want to explore it beforehand, you can zoom in and out with your mouse, and centre- or right-mouse press-drag to move around (you may need to select the blue left-pointing “pan” arrow-head on the left-hand-side menu). Note: the board will not be completely ready until the workshop, i.e. we are still working on it.